

**STUDENTS' SPEECH COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR IN THE
FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE
FUTURE SPECIALISTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES**

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The development of the education system in our country is a priority of state policy. The tasks of reforming this most important sphere, in which the future of the state is concentrated, are being solved in stages. One of the seven priority directions of the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is the development of human capital. The objectives of the Strategy include, among other tasks, raising the knowledge and qualifications of teaching staff to the international level.

Along with this, the issue of improving the quality of teaching foreign languages, including Russian, is also being considered here through the introduction of new pedagogical and information and communication technologies. Today, the improvement and reform of the education system in our country continues consistently and purposefully. The country has created a legal framework for improving the training of university graduates who possess the necessary professional competencies at a high level.

Speaking about the professional competence of university graduates, we should keep in mind, among other things, the formation of communicative competence.

Mastering the communicative competence of a university graduate affects his competitiveness in the labor market, successful socialization in the future. However, in recent years, teachers, psychologists, linguists, and specialists in other fields of knowledge have noted that the level of students' mastery of communicative competence is not high enough and does not fully meet the requirements of higher

professional education, although this competence is the most important component of the professional training of a future specialist. This fact indicates that the development of the communicative competence of a university student is one of the priorities of higher professional education.

And one of the important issues in the field of improving the quality of education is the introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the educational process.

Currently, the problem of developing the communicative competence of university students in classes in language disciplines has not been sufficiently developed.

Today we are witnessing a decrease in the level of general literacy, inability to use speech means of expression.

For the successful implementation of tasks on the formation of speech competence, it is possible to use a personality-oriented approach, which can become the basis for determining forms and methods for organizing subject-subject interaction.

The theory of communication convinces us that it is not enough to know the language, the language system, the rules of functioning of the language code. To communicate, you need to know how to use language in a certain context, i.e. to learn a language today means to master speech behavior in a natural context.

The specificity of language learning is such that it is a means of studying all other disciplines.

The goals of language teaching are known to be personal, meta-subject and subject, which in turn have such sub-goals as the ability and readiness for self-development, interdisciplinary knowledge, cognitive, communicative, etc.

The competence approach is the most effective in teaching the speech aspect of the language. When forming competencies, we must pay special attention to the formation and mastery of various types of speech activity; the basics of the culture of oral and written speech; the implementation of the speech-thinking process; the creation and reproduction of speech in accordance with the target communicative

attitude. Also important is the cultural approach, i.e. language acquisition through the development of the norms of Russian speech etiquette, the culture of interethnic communication. The main techniques of the interactive methodology are language learning in the community, learning in collaboration.

Here you can use various teaching methods. Y.K. Babansky offers methods of organizing educational activities; methods of stimulating and motivating cognitive activity; a method of control and self-control. A.V. Dudnikov offers inductive and deductive methods and their combination. L.P. Fedorenko offers such a method as sources of knowledge, which uses techniques such as questions (direct analytical, synthetic, rhetorical, suggestive, etc.); the reception of drawing up a plan on the go; recording the main provisions of the message; drawing up a reference summary, tables, diagrams, etc. communication, reflecting the historical experience of the people.

A number of methodologists offer text analysis, exposition, composition as a type of work on speech development.

M.I. Makhmutov provides a justification for problem-based learning as a didactic system and type of learning. The method of problem-based learning is presented in the form of a structure: problem problem + problem situation.

It is the flexible combination of different methods of teaching Russian based on the cultural aspect, used in the classroom together with a variety of teaching technologies, that will contribute to the motivation of students and efficiency in mastering languages in the future.

Thus, we can say that the technology of forming the rhetorical competence of a future specialist is the formation of cognitive, practical–activity and personal components.

The process of forming the rhetorical competence of a future specialist is a certain set of forms, methods and ways of forming rhetorical knowledge, rhetorical skills and personal orientations.

It is necessary to develop programs for the gradual formation of rhetorical competence, a set of tools and methods, techniques for the formation of a culture of speech that could be widely used with the help of information and communication technologies.

However, to date, scientific research devoted to the theoretical justification and practice of applying the technology of forming students' speech competence using electronic learning tools is not sufficiently presented.

Taking into account modern requirements for the organization of the educational process and with the transition to a new format of training, we must also solve the problems of improving distance learning. It seems relevant to create electronic resources where interactive forms of learning would be widely represented, since the formation of communication skills will be most effective precisely when the teacher and student work together.

The success of a modern person in any activity directly depends on his communicative competencies.

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